

**THE IMPACT OF COMMUNICATION STRATEGY AND COMMUNICATION
STYLE ON COMMUNICATION APPREHENSION: A QUANTITATIVE
STUDY WITH ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS**

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The Impact of Communication Strategy and Communication Style on Communication Apprehension: A Quantitative Study with English Major Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the impact of communication strategy and style on communication apprehension of English major students in a local college in Davao del Norte. The study is quantitative research that utilized a descriptive-correlational approach. A sample of 214 randomly selected English education students identified using stratified random sampling answered the surveys with three variables. Results showed that the level of communication apprehension, communication strategy, and communication style were all moderate. Results also revealed that there is a significant relationship between communication strategy and communication apprehension. Moreover, a significant relationship exists between communication style and apprehension among students. Hence, results show that the domains of communication strategy can significantly influence communication apprehension. Finally, it was revealed that domains of communication style, such as aggressive and passive, can significantly predict the communication apprehension of the respondents. Results imply that the variables are significant in overcoming the communication apprehension of English major students. This study recommends that educational institutions focus more on expanding and enhancing the knowledge and strategies of the students in understanding spoken messages, developing awareness in using communication styles, and improving self-confidence skills among students.

Keywords: *communication apprehension, communication strategy, communication style, English major students, Philippines*

Introduction

People's degree of worry or apprehension related to actual or planned communication with another person or individual is known as communication apprehension. Public speaking anxiety, which is frequently accompanied by shyness and anxiety, can cause severe anxiety and have a detrimental effect on interpersonal, intellectual, and social communication. A high percentage of communication apprehension is a characteristic of learners in the educational field, which limits their capacity to learn, impedes their ability to communicate with classmates, promotes social disengagement, and hinders their learning process. As a result, students experience increased stress and anxiety during class debates, which frequently turns into a fear of being misunderstood by their peers. Nevertheless, students can manage communication apprehension through strategies, but understanding how specific factors like communication strategy and style influence it, especially in English education, remains a gap (Bragg, 2017).

In international settings, particularly in Malaysia, students are experiencing difficulty in learning and applying their oral communicative learning due to a lack of linguistic resources or poor strategy and linguistic competence, which results in the intended message being misunderstood, which leads to a communication breakdown or error. In addition, in America, 70% of the students feel apprehensive when speaking publicly or just thinking about having a public appearance. Some students have confidence in their personalities, whereas others need to practice speaking in front of both large and small group settings. It is caused by schools focusing on various skills in the liberal arts tradition rather than developing the student's skills in different areas (Kuen et al., 2017).

In the Philippines, communication apprehension among students is evident. It is somewhat experienced by everyone to some extent, and feelings of timidity, anxiousness, and stress accompany it, which affects everyone, including the student's academic achievements. Moreover, the percentage of students having communication apprehension increased during and after the pandemic; since learners are learning online with the help of their devices, they are not able to experience face-to-face interaction with other people, especially speaking or presenting in front of a massive amount of people, which led to a decrease in their self-confidence (Dalan, 2023).

For this reason, the researcher decided to conduct this study to recognize the students' communication apprehension concretely and also to know the impact of communication strategy and style on the student's communication apprehension. Further, this research was also conducted to recognize what type of communication style is more effective and efficient for the students or what communication strategies the students mostly like nowadays. In addition, this study was conducted to determine how and if these variables can help students overcome their apprehension and how they can use them to overcome and learn effectively. Also, this study is relevant to improving the community as it could give essential and additional information to the community that would give new knowledge and perspective regarding communication apprehension and its effect on the students and the people in the community experiencing it.

In connection, studies such as "Communication Apprehension when Speaking English (L2): A Case Study of Personnel in an Organization Taking Care of Public Health Located in the Suburb of Bangkok, Thailand" (Booncherd & Rimkeeratikul, 2017) "Communication Apprehension in the Workplace: Focusing on Inclusion" (Cardon et al., 2022) which focuses solely on communication apprehension and its effect to individuals of all professional background, excluding the influence of communication strategy and style to communication apprehension, and "Oral Communication Apprehension in Oral Presentation among Polytechnic Students" by Gee

et al. (2021), focuses on examining the impact of communication strategy on communication apprehension. Thus, to address this gap, the researcher sees the need to conduct a study that determines the impact of communication strategy and style on a student's communication apprehension, as previous studies only showed the effect of communication apprehension without considering the influence of communication style. This study also intends to recognize how the communication style and strategy positively and negatively impact the students' communication apprehension, which is not shown in the previous studies.

The researcher has created a thorough dissemination plan that will help spread the study's significant findings. After finding the result of the study, the researcher aims to share the result with the Commission on Higher Education, English major students, communication researchers, parents, and English instructors, which were disseminated through online platforms, publication sites, and other academic networking sites. Further, the researcher created a video presentation containing the content and discussion of the study that will be sent and posted on Google Drive and can be accessed by those people who have approved. Also, the researcher provided a hardbound copy to be put inside the institution's library. This may help the study to spread across all target audiences.

Research Objectives

This study aims to determine the impact of communication strategy and communication style on communication apprehension. Specifically, it sought to address the following:

1. To determine the level of communication strategies of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1. strategies to cope with communication difficulties;
 - 1.2. strategies to understand the Interlocutor's message and
 - 1.3. strategies to carry on the conversation as intended.
2. To determine the level of communication style of the students in terms of:
 - 2.1. aggressive;
 - 2.2. passive; and
 - 2.3. assertive.
3. To determine the level of students' communication apprehension in terms of:
 - 3.1. group discussion;
 - 3.2. meeting;
 - 3.3. dyadic; and
 - 3.4. public speech.
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. communication strategy and communication apprehension; and
 - 4.2. communication style and communication apprehension.
5. To determine which domain of Communication Strategy and Communication Style influence Communication Apprehension.

Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative descriptive correlational research design was used in this study. The primary goal of this design was to look at how communicative strategy and communicative style can impact the communication apprehension of English major students. The research approach entails gathering and evaluating numerical data to quantify various variables, aiming to collect and derive meaningful insights. It can examine causation, generate hypotheses, detect trends and averages, and extrapolate results to more significant populations. In contrast, qualitative research gathers and examines non-numerical data (Bhandari, 2020).

A quantitative research methodology was adopted in the study context since it makes numerical data measurement and analysis possible, which were essential for finding patterns, generating hypotheses, and assessing causal links between variables. In addition, using descriptive-correlational research design facilitated exploring the relationships between communicative apprehension, communicative strategy, and communicative style among the research participants. Lastly, the results were generalized to a larger population, enabled by applying statistical analysis, which raised the study's outward consistency. Consequently, it was appropriate to adopt a quantitative research strategy for this study since it comprehensively examined the relationships between the factors of interest in an organized and impartial manner.

Moreover, Descriptive correlational research seeks to explain the link between two or more variables without establishing a cause-and-effect relationship. Determining whether two variables are connected requires gathering and evaluating data about at least two. Descriptive correlational research helps researchers understand factors and their relationships without altering them or assuming causality, aiming to provide a comprehensive explanation without altering variables. In addition, descriptive correlational research observes and quantifies variables without altering them or examining relationships between causes and effects. The independent variable is measured before the dependent variable in descriptive correlational research, which uses correlational designs to gauge the direction and degree of correlations between variables. Its objectives are to examine the connections between independent and dependent variables and to elucidate certain population traits or behaviors. Descriptive correlational research evaluates patterns and

correlations in data using correlational designs, while experimental research employs the independent variable to examine its effect on the dependent variable (Bhat, 2023).

The impact of communication strategy and style on the communication anxiety of English major students was measured in this study using a quantitative research design and a descriptive-correlational analysis approach. This research encompassed three key variables: communication strategy and style as independent factors and communication apprehension as the dependent variable. The study respondents consisted of students enrolled in English programs.

Furthermore, regression was employed in this study as a statistical tool to evaluate the relationship or relationships between one or more independent variables and a dependent variable. Additionally, regression analysis is frequently used to estimate and predict the dependent variable's conditional expectation given the independent factors, where its use intersects with machine learning (Yang, 2017).

In the context of the study, the regression adaptation was used to find the best connection and reasoning to predict the impact of communication strategy and style on the communication apprehension of English major students.

Respondents

The research occurred at a local college in Davao del Norte province. The researcher employed a random sample technique to find participants. Among the 457 English education students across all year levels in the first semester of the 2023-2024 academic year, 214 students were chosen as the study's sample. In the first year, there were 104 students, while in the second year, there were 64 students; in the third year, there were 32 total students and 14 fourth-year students. The selection of these students as respondents was based on the study's focus on evaluating the impact of communication strategy and style on communication apprehension. Also, since the study was all about the students' communication apprehension, it was considered appropriate and justified to include students from the English education program at the chosen local college located at Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Applicable students were selected to be part of the study.

The study also involved stratified random sampling to guarantee participants. The criteria specified by the researcher were appropriate for the study. The following criteria were used to choose the participants: they were male or female, aged 17 years old and above, can have different cultural backgrounds, and English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology were recruited from varied levels of English education, guaranteeing representation from each year level. Also, volunteerism was accepted as long as the participants met the standard qualification for this research. In addition, students who were not English major students were excluded from participating in this study. This approach involved dividing the enormous population into smaller groups or strata based on a significant trait, allowing the researchers to accurately depict the general population because each group is proportionally included in the sample. To identify the sample, the researcher initially acquired demographic information from the official post of Office Registrar 21 on the college's bulletin board. After acquiring the data, the researcher will pass it on to a statistician who will compute the study's sample.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondent*

<i>Programs</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
BSEd-English	1st	223	104	22.85%
BSEd-English	2nd	136	64	13.94%
BSEd-English	3rd	69	32	7.07%
BSEd-English	4th	29	14	2.97%
Total		457	214	46.83%

The table provided the data on how respondents were distributed across different academic years within the English education student population. It showed that out of 457 total students, 22.85% are in their first year, 13.94% are in their second year, 7.07% are in their third year, and 2.97% are in their fourth year. The dataset comprised 214 respondents, including 104 first-year students, 64 second-year students, 32 third-year students, and 14 fourth-year students.

Instrument

The researcher employed modified survey instruments from online resources to quantify the elements. These modified surveys were employed in this investigation and underwent extensive expert evaluation before the research released questionnaires aimed at the students. The first set of questions assessed English major students' communication apprehension with its indicators: group discussion, meeting, dyadic, and public speaking. This was adopted from the study of McCroskey et al. (1985) with a reliability of .91.

In addition, the second set of questions focused on the communication strategy of the English major students with its indicators: strategies to cope with communication difficulties, strategies to understand the interlocutors' message, and strategies to carry on the conversation as intended which was adopted from the study of Zhao and Intaraprasert (2013) with a reliability of .84.

Moreover, the third set of questions focused on the student's communication style with its indicators: aggressive, passive, and assertive, which is adapted from the study of Bocar (2017) that have a reliability of .87. This showed that these questions have higher results than

the acceptable reliability of .70.

The Likert scale is a rating system used to assess attitudes, behaviors, or beliefs. It concludes with five or seven answer statements after beginning with a statement or query. The option best reflects the respondent's perspective on the statement or query chosen. Likert scales work best when used to measure characteristics that are difficult to measure, or that cannot be observed directly. These could be attitudes, feelings, or opinions that affect behavior (Bhandari & Nikolopoulou, 2020).

A Likert scale was employed to gauge the degree of agreement or disagreement with statements about how communication style and approach affect students' communication anxiety. This scale allowed the research to gather straightforward data to analyze and comprehend, helping assess participants' preparedness for self-directed learning, a crucial aspect of English education students. Participants were instructed to indicate their answers by marking a number associated with the checkbox. They were asked to utilize a five-point Likert scale ranging from 'always' to 'rarely.' Following this, the scores for these responses were combined across the items to provide participants with an overall score.

Procedure

The following steps were taken to collect the data for this study.

Questionnaire Formulation and Development. The researcher searched the questionnaires from reliable journal articles and related studies on the internet, which were positively related to the three variables.

Revision and Validation of Questionnaires. Afterward, it was presented to the panel of experts to be evaluated and contextualized towards English learning. The researcher followed the advice of those revision experts until it was approved for administration.

Requesting Permission to Conduct a Study. Once the questionnaires were ready for administration, permission to administer the study in the concerned institution was secured through a formal letter from the college's Vice President for Academic Affairs.

Distribution of Questionnaires. The research instruments were given directly to the respondents via Google Forms and face-to-face surveys with permission, and the researcher conducted the study.

Collection and Tabulation of Data. After performing the survey, the researcher took and analyzed the research instrument to record and tabulate the collected data or the survey responses from the respondents. The statistical data was analyzed, and the results were interpreted. From the final data, conclusions were drawn, and recommendations were presented based on the obtained results.

Data Analysis

The data in this study were calculated using the following statistical methods.

Mean. This was utilized to assess the quality of communication apprehension, communication strategy, and communication style among the respondents.

Pearson-r. This was utilized to know the significant relationship between the quality of the communication apprehension, communication strategy, and communication style of the respondents.

Regression. This was utilized to determine the significant impact of the respondents' communication apprehension, communication strategy, and communication style.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting research, the researcher needs to adhere to strong ethical guidelines. Therefore, these various measures have been developed in quantitative research to guarantee ethical integrity. The study's primary goal was to secure the health and welfare of the 214 participants involved. In this study, the researcher has embraced the ethical guidelines put forth by Denzin and Lincoln (2011). The focus of these guidelines dominantly revolves around three key areas: reducing the possibility of damage, getting informed consent, managing any conflicts of interest, and guaranteeing privacy and anonymity.

Informed Consent. Precise information regarding the study was provided to the participants; this includes the type of questions, the data's planned use, and any possible consequences before they participated in the research. In order to take part, people must give informed consent, meaning that the researcher must acknowledge their right to see their data and the freedom to leave the study whenever the respondents choose. The informed permission procedure acts as a contract between the participants and the researcher (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Within the Google forms and face-to-face survey interaction, the researcher included informed consent, asked permission to answer the survey questions, and inquired whether participants remained willing to participate in the study considering the potential dangers and the study's purpose. Furthermore, participants can say no if the deal does not convince them.

The informed consent process included instructions for participants about their diverse rights. They were told that they had the option to stop using involvement in the study without stating an explanation. Also, they possessed the choice to refuse to respond to delicate

inquiries. Additionally, attendees were allowed to enquire about any parts of the study they did not understand. Additionally, information regarding the study's findings was provided to them after the research had been completed.

Risk of Injury, Privacy, Secrecy and Confidentiality. Preserving the privacy of respondents' names and other personally identifiable information is among the personal data that is vital throughout the duration of the trial. This is an essential preventative step to avoid any potential harm or unfavorable effects that could result from the disclosure of their personal information. Additionally, anonymity is essential for avoiding any prejudices from impacting the study, so researchers are not swayed by the unique characteristics of individuals or personal names. In order to guarantee participants' confidentiality, the researcher used codes or false names in replacement of the participants' real names and put in place measures to ensure private information is gathered in confidence (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In order to protect the privacy of the data, the researcher did not collect the email addresses and phone numbers of participants. Furthermore, steps were taken to ensure the study's findings and the results were not made public and were kept private; Under Republic Act No. 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards individual personal information in information and communications systems used by the public and private sectors, the participants' personal information was safeguarded. This safety measure was designed to keep individuals from going through psychological distress including humiliation and guilt that comes from unintentional or unauthorized data exchange. Additionally, the data was stored securely and finally disposed of three years following the study's conclusion.

Conflicts of Interest. When the researcher has previous experience or relationships with the participant, it was crucial to openly disclose any acts that can result in a conflict of interest. When requesting ethical approval, mention that because of its transparency, the ethics committee offers advice on handling these disputes. Conflicts of interest can also occur when the researcher emphasizes putting their interests or commitments ahead of their work-related duties. These disputes may involve money and non-financial benefits, whether actual, potential, or even perceived. Conflicts of interest like this could affect or be seen as affecting the researcher's judgment and impartiality, which might undermine trust in the reliability of the findings from research (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Additionally, because the respondents were fellow students, the researcher has no conflicts of interest related to the research. Conflict of interest occurs only when the researcher has the power to force participants to participate using coercion, denying rewards, or applying fines (for instance, a student researcher working for the same institution can use their position of authority or pressure to force other students to take the survey. Also, suppose they are in a leadership role within the organization or have an influence on other students. In that case, the researcher uses this to pressure other students to participate in the study by promising rewards or threatening social repercussions if they do not participate).

Results and Discussion

This section presents and analyzes the respondents' answers about communication apprehension, communication strategy, and communication style. The topics discussed are the level of communication strategies, level of communication styles, and level of communication apprehension; the significant relationship between communication strategy and communication apprehension, and communication style and communication apprehension; and which domain of communication strategy and communication style influences communication apprehension of the English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology.

Level of Students' Communication Apprehension in terms of Group Discussion

The student's communication apprehension level was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator group discussion. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

The mean scores of the respondents' answers about their degree of communication anxiety about group discussions are shown in Table 2. According to the statistics, the students' overall mean score for communication anxiety during group discussions was 2.41, which is the descriptive equivalent of low. This suggested that students' communication anxiety seldom manifests during group discussions.

Table 2. The Level of Students' Communication Apprehension in terms of Group Discussion

<i>Group Discussion</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Trying not to participate in group discussions.	2.20	Low
2.	Feeling uncomfortable participating in group discussions.	2.44	Low
3.	Feeling tense and nervous while participating in group discussions.	2.80	Moderate
4.	Limiting myself from getting involved in group discussions.	2.24	Low
5.	Trying not to engage in any group discussion with new people since it makes me tense and nervous.	2.35	Low
Overall		2.41	Low

The highest mean score is 2.80, with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This mean was obtained from item no. 3 - Feeling tense and nervous while participating in group discussions means that the respondents sometimes manifest this item.

Furthermore, the data also revealed that the lowest mean score, which is 2.20 with a descriptive equivalent of low, was obtained from

item no. 1 - Trying not to participate in group discussions, which means that this item is seldom manifested.

Level of Students' Communication Apprehension in Terms of Meeting

The student's communication apprehension level was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator meeting. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

The average meeting scores are shown in Table 3. According to the data, the student's overall mean degree of communication anxiety throughout the meeting was 2.63, which is descriptively equivalent to low. This suggests that students' level of communication anxiety during meetings is seldom evident.

The highest mean score is 2.77, with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. The mean was obtained from item no. 4 - Having no confidence in myself in answering questions during meetings means that the respondents sometimes manifest this item.

The data also revealed that the lowest mean score, which is 2.52 with a descriptive equivalent of low, was obtained from item no. 2 - Meetings can make me tremble, which means that the respondents seldom manifest this item.

Table 3. *The Level of Students' Communication Apprehension in Terms of Meeting*

	Meeting	Mean	Description
1.	Participating in a meeting makes me nervous.	2.65	Low
2.	Meetings can make me tremble.	2.52	Low
3.	Expressing my thoughts during meetings is unachievable	2.62	Low
4.	Having no confidence in myself in answering questions during meetings.	2.77	Moderate
5.	Communicating at meetings usually makes me uncomfortable.	2.57	Low
	Overall	2.63	Low

This data shows that students generally experience low levels of anxiety during meetings, with a total mean of 2.63. While some students occasionally lack confidence when answering questions (mean score of 2.77), the feeling of fear or trembling in meetings is rarely felt (mean score of 2.52). This suggests that students do not often struggle with communication apprehension in meeting settings, though some moments of doubt do arise.

The Level of Students' Communication Apprehension in Terms of Dyadic

The level of students' communication apprehension was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator dyadic. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

The mean scores of the respondents' answers about their degree of dyadic communication anxiety are shown in Table 4. According to the findings, the student's overall mean score for dyadic communication anxiety was 2.72, which has the descriptive equivalent of moderate. This suggests that students occasionally exhibit a certain degree of dyadic communication anxiety.

The data revealed that the highest mean score of 2.85 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate was obtained from item no. 2 - Being nervous when conversing with a new acquaintance, which means that the respondents sometimes manifest this item.

Table 4. *The Level of Students' Communication Apprehension in Terms of Dyadic*

	Dyadic	Mean	Description
1.	Having fear of speaking up in conversations.	2.77	Moderate
2.	Being nervous when participating in a conversation with a new acquaintance.	2.85	Moderate
3.	Feeling tense and nervous in conversation.	2.71	Moderate
4.	Feeling nervous conversing with other students.	2.64	Low
5.	Being afraid to speak up in conversations.	2.64	Low
	OVERALL	2.72	Moderate

The data also revealed the lowest mean score of 2.64 with a descriptive equivalent of low, obtained from item no. 4 - Feeling nervous conversing with other students, and item no. 5, Being afraid to speak up in conversations, means that the respondents seldom manifest these two items.

Level of Students' Communication Apprehension in Terms of Public Speech

The student's communication apprehension level was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator of public speech. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

The mean scores of the respondents' answers about their degree of communication anxiety about public speaking are shown in Table 5. According to the statistics, students' overall mean degree of communication anxiety in terms of public speaking was 2.94, which is the descriptive equivalent of moderate. This suggests that students' communicative anxiety about public speaking occasionally shows up. The data revealed that the highest mean score of 3.09 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate was obtained from item no. 5 - Giving a speech makes me nervous, and I forget facts I know, which means that the respondents sometimes manifest this item.

Table 5. *The Level of Students' Communication Apprehension in Terms of Public Speech*

	<i>Public Speech</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Giving a speech in front of you is impossible.	2.68	Moderate
2.	Giving a speech makes certain parts of my body feel very tense and rigid.	2.97	Moderate
3.	Giving a speech makes my hands sweat.	2.92	Moderate
4.	Giving a speech makes my thoughts confused and jumbled.	3.03	Moderate
5.	Giving a speech makes me nervous, and I forget facts I know.	3.09	Moderate
	Overall	2.94	Moderate

The data also revealed that the lowest mean score, which is 2.68 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate, was obtained from item no. 1 - Giving a speech in front is impossible, which means that this item is also sometimes manifested by the respondents.

Summary of the Level of Communication Apprehension of the Students

The general level of communication anxiety among Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology English majors is displayed in Table 6. According to the statistics, public speech communication anxiety has the highest mean score, 2.94, with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This suggests that the degree of communicative anxiety related to public speaking occasionally shows up.

On the other hand, the respondents also sometimes manifested dyadic behavior. A mean rating of 2.63 for meeting as an indicator of communication apprehension with a descriptive equivalent of low according to the respondents' scores on the following items taken from the study tool. The low level showed that pupils rarely displayed this specific signal.

Moreover, group discussion is seldom manifested by the respondents. Also, the gathered data shows that the lowest mean is the group discussion, which gathered the lowest mean score of 2.41. The indication group conversation received an overall mean rating of 2.41, considered low. The low level of this indicator showed that students rarely displayed communication anxiety during group discussions.

Lastly, the meeting was also seldom manifested by the respondents. Based on respondents' ratings as indications of communication anxiety, the dyadic received a moderate mean rating of 2.72. The intermediate level showed that the students occasionally displayed this specific signal.

Table 6. *Summary of the Level of Communication Apprehension of the Students*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Group Discussion	2.41	Low
Meeting	2.63	Low
Dyadic	2.72	Moderate
Public Speech	2.94	Moderate
Overall	2.67	Moderate

Level of Communication Strategies of the Students in Terms of Strategies to Cope with Communication Difficulties

The level of communication strategies of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator strategies to cope with communication difficulties. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

The mean scores of the respondents' answers about their degree of communication strategies in terms of coping mechanisms for communication challenges are shown in Table 7. According to the statistics, the students' overall mean score for communication methods to deal with communication challenges was 3.58, which is the descriptive equivalent of high. This showed that the student's degree of communication strategy in terms of coping mechanisms for communication problems frequently shows up.

Table 7. *The level of Communication Strategies of the Students in Terms of Strategies to Cope with Communication Difficulties*

	<i>Strategies to Cope with Communication Difficulties</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Using familiar words, phrases, or sentences to gain confidence when communicating.	3.64	High
2.	Correcting my pronunciation, grammar, and lexical mistakes to improve communication skills.	3.91	High
3.	Using nonverbal language, such as body language, to express my thoughts.	3.62	High
4.	Writing or spelling out the intended words, phrases, or sentences to improve communication skills.	3.73	High
5.	Requesting the instructor to verify my comprehension.	3.00	Moderate
	Overall	3.58	High

The highest mean score is 3.91, which is a descriptive equivalent of high. This mean was obtained from item no. 2 - Correcting my pronunciation, grammar, and lexical mistakes to improve communication skills, which means that the respondents oftentimes manifest

this item.

Hence, the data also revealed that the lowest mean score which is 3.00 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate was obtained from item no. 5 Requesting the instructor to verify my comprehension which means that the respondents sometimes manifest this item.

Level of Communication Strategies of the Students in Terms of Strategies to Understand the Interlocutor's Message

The level of communication strategies of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator strategies to understand the interlocutor's message. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 8. *The level of Communication Strategy of the Students in Terms of Strategies to Understand the Interlocutors' Message*

<i>Strategies to Understand the Interlocutors' Message</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Asking the teacher to slow down when speaking.	2.52	Low
2.	Asking the teacher to simplify the language.	2.72	Moderate
3.	Asking the teacher to give an example when I feel confused.	2.91	Moderate
4.	Trying to catch teachers' main points during discussions.	3.57	High
5.	Trying to guess the meaning of what the teacher has said.	3.47	High
Overall		3.04	Moderate

The mean scores of the respondents' answers about their degree of communication strategy in terms of methods to comprehend the message of the interlocutor are shown in Table 8. According to the statistics, students' communication methods for comprehending the interlocutor's message had a mean score of 3.04 overall, the descriptive equivalent of moderate. This suggests that students' communication skills in terms of comprehending the interlocutor's message are occasionally demonstrated.

The highest mean score is 3.57, which is a descriptive equivalent of high. The mean was obtained from item 5 - Trying to catch teachers' main point during the discussion, which also means that the respondents often manifest this item.

The data also revealed that the lowest mean score, which is 2.52, with a descriptive equivalent of low, was obtained from item no. 1 - Asking the teacher to slow down when speaking, this indicates that the respondents seldom manifest this item.

Level of Communication Strategies of the Students in Terms of Strategies to Carry on the Conversation as Intended

The student's communication strategy level was measured through a survey questionnaire with indicator strategies to carry on the conversation as intended. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 9. *Level of Communication Strategies of the Students in Terms of Strategies to Carry on the Conversation as Intended*

<i>Strategies to Carry on the Conversation as Intended</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Trying to enjoy the conversation.	3.65	High
2.	Sending signals to show my understanding, such as nodding.	3.82	High
3.	Feeling all right for taking risks while speaking.	3.38	Moderate
4.	Feeling all right if the conversation does not go smoothly by keeping talking.	3.22	Moderate
5.	Responding to the teacher despite an imperfect understanding of the message.	3.27	Moderate
Overall		3.47	High

The mean scores of the respondents' answers about their degree of communication strategy—that is, how they plan to continue the conversation as intended—are shown in Table 9. With a descriptive equivalent of high, the data showed that the students' overall mean score for communication strategies—that is, techniques to continue the conversation as intended—was 3.47.

This demonstrated the pupils' level of communication strategy, which frequently manifests in ways to continue the conversation as intended.

The data revealed that the highest mean score, 3.82, with a descriptive equivalent of high, was obtained from item no. 2 - Sending signals to show my understanding, such as nodding, which means that the respondents oftentimes manifest this item.

The data also revealed that the lowest mean score, which is 3.22 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate, was obtained from item no. 4 - Feeling all right if the conversation does not go smoothly by keeping talking, this indicates that the respondents sometimes manifest this item.

Summary of the Level of Communication Strategies of the Students

Shown in Table 10 is the overall level of the communication strategy of the English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology in terms of strategies to cope with communication difficulties, strategies to understand the interlocutors' message, and strategies to carry on the conversation as intended.

Table 10. *Summary of the Level of Communication Strategies of the Students*

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. Strategies to cope with communication difficulties	3.58	High
2. Strategies to understand the interlocutors' message	3.04	Moderate
3. Strategies to carry on the conversation as intended	3.47	High
Overall	3.36	Moderate

The data revealed that the students sometimes manifested the level of communication strategy in terms of strategies to cope with communication difficulty. The result also shows that the highest mean is the strategies to cope with communication difficulties, with the highest mean score of 3.58 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of communication strategy in terms of strategies to cope with communication difficulties is oftentimes manifested.

Also, the students sometimes manifested this message in terms of strategies to understand the interlocutors' message. This also resulted in the lowest mean, with a mean score of 3.04 and a descriptive equivalent of moderate. The moderate level of this indicator indicated that the communication strategy of the students in terms of strategies to understand the interlocutors' message was sometimes manifested.

Moreover, the respondents sometimes manifested the strategies to carry on the conversation as intended. Based on the respondents' evaluations of the following items taken from the research instrument, the mean rating was 3.47, resulting in a high description. The high level showed that the students frequently displayed this specific signal.

Level of Communication Style of the Students in Terms of Aggressive

The level of communication style of the students was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator aggressive. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

The mean scores of the respondents' answers about their degree of aggressive communication style are shown in Table 11. According to the statistics, the students' overall mean communication style score was 2.14, which is the descriptive equivalent of low. These findings suggested that students' aggressive communication style is rarely seen.

Table 11. *The Level of Communication Style of the Students in Terms of Aggressive*

Aggressive	Mean	Description
1. Being close-minded and would not give a thought to other people's point-of-view.	2.23	Low
2. Trying not to listen to other people's point-of-view.	2.10	Low
3. Having difficulty seeing other people's point-of-view.	2.37	Low
4. Interrupting while others are talking.	1.95	Low
5. Monopolizing in times of conversation.	2.07	Low
Overall	2.14	Low

The highest mean score is 2.37, which is a descriptive equivalent of low. This mean was obtained from item no. 3 - Having difficulty seeing the other person's point of view, which means that this item is seldom manifested by the respondents. Hence, the data also revealed that the lowest mean score, which is 1.95 with a descriptive equivalent of low, was obtained from item no. 4 - Interrupting while others are talking, which means that the respondents seldom manifest this item.

Level of Communication Style of the Students in Terms of Passive

The student's communication style level was measured through a survey questionnaire with the passive indicator. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 12. *Level of Communication Style of the Students in Terms of Passive*

Passive	Mean	Description
1. Trying to indirectly relay the message to my classmates.	2.59	Low
2. Trying to always agree with other people's thoughts.	3.06	Moderate
3. Trying not to speak up my thoughts.	2.99	Moderate
4. Hesitating to share my ideas with my classmates/teacher.	3.09	Moderate
5. Letting my classmates always speak their thoughts.	3.55	Low
Overall	3.06	Moderate

The mean scores of the respondents' answers on their degree of passive communication style are shown in Table 12. According to the data, the student's overall mean passive communication style was 3.06, the descriptive equivalent of moderate. This suggested that the student's degree of passive communication style occasionally shows up.

The highest mean score is 3.55, which is a descriptive equivalent of high. The mean was obtained from item no. 5 - Letting my classmates always speak their thoughts, which means that the respondents oftentimes manifest this item. The data also revealed that the lowest mean score, which is 2.59 with a descriptive equivalent of low, was obtained from item no.1 - Trying to indirectly relay the

message to my classmates, which means that the respondents seldom manifest this item.

Level of Communication Style of the Students in Terms of Assertive

The student's communication style level was measured through a survey questionnaire with the indicator assertive. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

The mean scores of the respondents' answers about their degree of aggressive communication style are shown in Table 13. According to the data, the student's overall mean forceful communication style was 3.78, which is the descriptive equivalent of high. This suggested that the student's degree of forceful communication style is frequently demonstrated.

The data revealed that the highest mean score of 4.07 with a descriptive equivalent of high was obtained from item no. 1 - Trying to always listen to my teacher/classmates to have effective communication, which means that the respondents oftentimes manifest this item.

Table 13. *Level of Communication Style of the Students in Terms of Assertive*

	<i>Assertive</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Trying to always listen to my teacher/classmates to have effective communication.	4.07	High
2.	Trying to state my limitations or expectations when having communication.	3.73	High
3.	Stating my observations and with no judgment.	3.71	High
4.	Expressing myself directly, and honestly about my feelings and wants, and as soon as possible.	3.63	High
5.	Trying to check on others' feelings when negatively commented.	3.83	High
	Overall	3.79	High

The data also revealed that the lowest mean score, which is 3.63, with a descriptive equivalent of high, was obtained from item no. 4 - Expressing myself directly and honestly about my feelings and wants, and as soon as possible, this indicates that the respondents oftentimes manifest this item.

Summary of the Level of Communication Style of the Students

Shown in Table 14 is the overall level of communication style of the English major students in terms of aggressive, passive, and assertive. The data revealed that the respondents sometimes manifested a level of communication style in terms of passive. According to the respondents' ratings of the following items taken from the study instrument, this also had a mean rating of 3.06, considered moderate. The intermediate level showed that the students occasionally displayed this specific signal.

Also, the data revealed that the respondents seldom manifested an aggressive style, which gained the lowest mean score of 2.14. The indication of aggressiveness received a low overall mean rating of 2.14. The low level of this indication showed that students rarely displayed an aggressive communication style while communicating. Lastly, it was shown that the respondents oftentimes manifested assertiveness, which has a descriptive equivalent of high and the highest mean score of 3.79. This suggests that the degree of assertiveness of the communication style is frequently displayed.

Table 14. *Summary of the Level of Communication Style of the Students*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Aggressive	2.14	Low
Passive	3.06	Moderate
Assertive	3.79	High
Overall	3.00	Moderate

Significant Relationship Between Communication Strategy and Communication Apprehension

As shown in Table 15, there is a significant relationship between communication strategy and communication apprehension. The table shows that the mean of communication strategy is 3.36 and 2.67 for communication apprehension, which resulted in the r-value being .137 or $r(114) = .137$.

Table 15. *The Significance of the Relationship between Communication Strategy and Communication Apprehension of Students*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>R-Value</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision $\alpha=0.05$</i>
Communication Strategy	3.36	.137	.046	Ho Rejected
Communication Apprehension	2.67			

Consequently, the correlation between communication strategy and communication style is 13% significant, and 87% is the unknown relationship between the two. The figure also shows the probability value, which is $p < .046$. There is a positive, moderate, and significant

link between communication strategy and communication style, as indicated by the rejection of the null hypothesis since the probability value ($p < .046$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Significant Relationship Between Communication Style and Communication Apprehension

As shown in Table 16, there is a significant relationship between communication style and communication apprehension. The table shows that the mean of communication style is 3.00 and 2.67 for communication apprehension, resulting in the r -value being .431 or $r(114) = .431$. Therefore, 43% of the relationship between communication style and communication apprehension is significant, and 57% is the unknown relationship between the two variables. The table also shows the probability value, which is $p < .001$. The null hypothesis is rejected since the probability value ($p = .001$) is less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$). This indicates that communication apprehension and communication style have a positive, moderate, and substantial association

Table 16. *The Significant Relationship Between Communication Style and Communication Apprehension*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision $\alpha=0.05$
Communication Style	3.00	.431	<.001	Ho Rejected
Communication Apprehension	2.67			

Regression Analysis on the Domain/s of Communication Strategy that Influences Communication Apprehension

Presented in Table 17 is the regression analysis on the domain/s of communication strategy that influences communication apprehension of the English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. The data shows that all three domains of communication strategy, strategies to cope with communication difficulties, strategies to understand the interlocutor's message, and strategies to carry on the conversation as intended, appear to be statistically significant predictors of the level of communication apprehension of English education students – strategies to cope with communication difficulties ($\beta = 0.176$, $p = 0.025$), strategies to understand the interlocutor's message ($\beta = 0.195$, $p = 0.011$), and strategies to carry on the conversation as intended ($\beta = -0.232$, $p = 0.004$). At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected.

According to the beta value, $\beta = 0.195$, the degree of communication anxiety among English major students will drop by 0.195 units for every unit of communication strategy used to comprehend the interlocutor's message. Similarly, the beta value, $\beta = 0.176$, shows that communication anxiety among English major students will drop by 0.176 units for every unit of communication strategies to deal with communication challenges. Furthermore, the beta value, $\beta = -0.232$, shows that students' communication anxiety will drop by -0.232 units for every unit of methods to continue the talk as planned. As a result, all three communication strategy indicators had a substantial impact on English major students' communication anxiety.

Table 17. *Regression Analysis on the Domain/s of Communication Strategy that Influences Communication Apprehension*

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.674	0.054			
Strategies to cope with communication difficulties	0.176	0.078	0.192	0.025	Ho Rejected
Strategies to understand the interlocutor's message	0.195	0.076	0.203	0.011	Ho Rejected
Strategies to carry on the conversation as intended	-0.232	0.079	-0.236	0.004	Ho Rejected
Dependent Variable: Communication Apprehension					
Note	R=0.292, R2 =0.085, F-ratio=6.522, P-value= <.001				

In addition, communication strategy explained a significant proportion of variance in communication apprehension, $R^2 = 0.085$, $F = 6.522$, $p < .001$. The R^2 of 0.085 shows that the model predicts 85% of the statistical variation observed in the respondents' communication apprehension level. The coefficient of alienation, which is 15%, points to the extent to which other indicators or domains not included in the study may explain the variance observed in the level of communication apprehension among English major students.

Regression Analysis on the Domain/s of Communication Style that Influences Communication Apprehension

Presented in Table 18 is the regression analysis on the domain/s of communication style that influences communication apprehension of the English major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. T

he data shows that two domains of communication style – aggressive and passive – appear to be statistically significant predictors of the level of communication apprehension of the English major students – aggressive ($\beta = 0.162$, $p = 0.004$) and passive ($\beta = 0.377$, $p < .001$). The null hypothesis has been rejected at the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 18. Regression Analysis on the Domain/s of Communication Style that Influences Communication Apprehension

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.674	0.054			
Aggressive	0.162	0.055	0.197	0.004	Ho Rejected
Passive	0.377	0.075	0.358	<.001	Ho Rejected
Assertive	0.013	0.061	0.014	0.832	Ho Accepted
Dependent Variable: Communication Apprehension					
Note	R=0.477, R ² =0.227, F-ratio=20.0601, P-value= <.001				

The beta value of $\beta=0.377$ indicates that for every unit increase in passive style, the level of communication apprehension among English major students will also decrease by 0.377 units. Likewise, the beta value of $\beta=0.162$ indicates that for every unit increase in aggressive style, the level of communication apprehension among English major students will also decrease by 0.162 units. Therefore, passive and aggressive are the indicators of communication style that can significantly influence the communication apprehension of English major students.

On the other hand, the assertive style ($\beta=0.013$, $p=0.832$) does not significantly influence communication apprehension. At a 0.05 level of significance, the p-value of the domain exceeded 0.05. This implies that the domain does not significantly predict communication anxiety.

Moreover, communication style explained a significant proportion of variance in communication apprehension, $R^2=0.227$, $F=20.0601$, $p<.001$. The R^2 of 0.227 shows that the model predicts 22.7% of the statistical variation observed in the respondents' communication apprehension level. The coefficient of alienation, which is 77.3%, points to the extent to which other indicators or domains not included in the study may explain the variance observed in the level of communication apprehension among English major students.

Conclusions

Drawing upon the results, conclusions were formulated in response to the questions posed in the preceding chapter. The respondents consistently reported a significant prevalence of communication strategy, indicating that the students sometimes observe this variable.

Based on the result of the communication strategy as perceived by students, it was determined to be moderate. This means that the students sometimes observe the presence of the variable. Moreover, based on the result of the communication style of the students, it can also be drawn that the level of communication style of the students was moderate. This means that the students sometimes manifested the variable. In addition, the student's communication apprehension was also determined to be moderate. This means that the communication apprehension of the English primary students is sometimes manifested.

Furthermore, the correlation between communication strategy and communication apprehension revealed a significant relationship between the two variables. The study shows that communication strategy has a moderate, positive, and significant relationship with communication apprehension among English major students. This means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

Moreover, the correlation between communication style and communication apprehension also revealed a significant relationship between the two variables. The study also shows that communication style has a moderate, positive, and significant relationship with communication apprehension among English major students. This means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

Based on the result of regression analysis, in communication strategy, all three domains have shown significant influence on communication apprehension. This means that the domains – strategies to cope with communication difficulties, understand the interlocutor's message, and carry on the conversation as intended – are significant predictors of communication apprehension of English major students. Accordingly, the model describes 8.5% of the statistical variation with an $F=6.522$ and $p<.001$ in the communication apprehension of the respondents. In comparison, the remaining 91.5% refers to the other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the communication apprehension of the respondents.

Lastly, the regression analysis of communication style has two domains that significantly influence the communication apprehension of the respondents. This means that the aggressive and passive domains are significant predictors of communication apprehension. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model described 22.7% of the statistical variation with an $F=20.0601$ and $p<.001$ in the communication apprehension of the respondents. In comparison, the remaining 77.3% refers to the other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the communication apprehension of the respondents.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were formulated. Among the communication strategy indicators, it was found that strategies to understand the interlocutor's message have the lowest mean. Therefore, the following recommendations are given.

It is hereby recommended that the educational institution focus on expanding and enhancing the knowledge and strategies of the

students in understanding spoken messages. This could involve the collaboration of the speaker and listener, using shallow words in the discussion, and further assistance and questioning of the students if they have understood the discussions. Regular updates of students' knowledge of vocabulary may also be considered. Repeating words may also help students slowly overcome anxiety when speaking in class.

Based on the results, aggressive has been identified as having the lowest mean among the communication style indicators. Consequently, a set of target recommendations was formulated to maintain this aspect.

Therefore, it is recommended that educational institutions be aware of neglecting this kind of style when speaking to students. This type of communication style may influence their future and shatter their endeavors. It is now recommended that institutions know how to handle students who have acquired this style since this may cause apprehension in the students around them and cause further emotional and physical damage.

The findings also revealed that public speech produced the highest mean among communication apprehension indicators. The findings emphasize the need for improvement in the public speech of the students. Therefore, the following recommendations are given.

It is recommended that educational institutions and instructors focus on fostering self-confidence among students. This can be achieved by making students feel at ease speaking in front of people. It is further recommended that instructors should practice students more on speaking in front of the class to practice and get used to it.

Moreover, for the benefit of future researchers, a recommendation is made to consider employing a mixed-method approach when delving into the intricate interplay between communication strategy, communication style, and communication apprehension. Although the present study centered on a quantitative research design involving 214 students, utilizing a mixed-method approach holds promise for multiple reasons. Integrating quantitative data from surveys with qualitative insights obtained through interviews or focus groups provides a comprehensive presentation of students' perspectives.

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